
**Links between needs of
international stakeholders
(FAO, OIE, WHO) and One
Health EJP expertise**

**WP5 Science to policy
translation to stakeholders**

Responsible Partner: BfR, SSI

GENERAL INFORMATION

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LINKS BETWEEN NEEDS OF INTERNATIONAL STAKEHOLDERS (FAO, OIE, WHO) AND ONE HEALTH EJP EXPERTISE

Introduction

The [One Health European Joint Programme](#) (One Health EJP) aims to create a sustainable European framework by integration and alignment of medical, veterinary and food safety institutes that perform reference laboratory functions. The organisations unite forces through joint prioritization and conduction of research, integrative activities, and training and education exercises in the domains of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats, thus matching the needs of European and national policy makers and stakeholders. Through this One Health approach, the consortium strengthens its preparedness according to the 'prevent-detect-response' concept.

All One Health EJP partners have the mandate of their national or regional authorities (i.e. Ministries competent for foodborne zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance: mainly ministries of public health and agriculture, and national food agencies). As such, the One Health EJP has a privileged position when it comes to feeding back its outcomes to national and European policy makers and risk managers.

Although research is an important element for the One Health EJP activities, it predominantly focuses on bringing together scientists interested in public health, animal health and food safety. The essential objective of the One Health EJP is to stimulate this inter-sector collaboration by building capacities, sharing methodologies, databases and surveillance data, harmonisation of procedures, etc.

Connecting to other international organizations and networks obviously reinforces the One Health EJP's scientific objectives, broadens the scope of the One Health approach, offers exciting opportunities for research and adds to the international and global visibility of the One Health EJP.

Purpose

The One Health EJP has already active collaboration with ECDC and EFSA. Recently the potential influence that One Health EJP can have at international level has been acknowledged, and we have been encouraged to "go global". As part of this process we want to create formal links with three major global stakeholders: FAO, OIE and WHO (Europe).

The purpose of this document is to give an overview on the possible impact work carried out in the One Health EJP can have for these stakeholders and to guide interested parties to collect more detailed information by visiting the One Health EJP website or contact the research teams directly.

Identified needs

This document lists research and integrative needs of the international stakeholders FAO, OIE and WHO, identified by the One Health EJP work package involved in science to policy translation by scanning open access documents considered most relevant for the topics antimicrobial resistance (AMR), foodborne

zoonoses (FBZ) and emerging threats (ET). It also relates these needs with the activities of One Health EJP Joint Integrative and Research Projects (JIPs and JRPs) implemented during the first round of projects (2018-2020).

The table below is divided in 2 horizontal sections delimited by the vertical text in the leftmost column.

- The first section is a list of general One Health needs of international stakeholders.
- The second section lists specific identified research and integrative needs in which One Health EJP has strong expertise.

1. Column “FAO/OIE/WHO needs”

Here we listed the identified perceived relevant research and integrative needs of international stakeholders FAO, OIE and WHO. The main procedure for the identification of needs is the scanning of online available documents (publications, reports, guidelines etc.) in the fields AMR, FBZ and ET published by the mentioned international stakeholders or directly linked to them. The scanned documents deal with specific, technical topics, as well as general policy guidelines. The aim is to identify requirements and knowledge gaps that potentially may be resolved by the ongoing or future work of activities within One Health EJP. Attention is given to knowledge gaps requiring an intersectoral, multidisciplinary approach for their closure, i.e. a One Health approach.

2. Column “Highlights of ONE HEALTH EJP JIPs and JRPs”

Each identified need is related with topics of Joint Research Projects (JRP) or Joint Integrative Projects (JIP) of the 1st round of projects of One Health EJP that are dealing directly or indirectly with the mentioned need. The brief summary text highlights how One Health EJP is tackling the issue, and supports easy access to our website.

	Identified FAO/OIE/WHO needs	Highlights of One Health EJP JIPs and JRPs
General needs [1-14]	One Health approach to address the issue of AMR, FBZ and ET.	OneHealth EJP modus operandi
	Coordination between international actors and global partnership between institutions dealing with animal health, human health and food safety, in developed and developing countries.	<p>One Health EJP formalizes One Health partnership within countries and across Europe.</p> <p>ECDC and EFSA are important European One Health EJP stakeholders and actively follow up the integrative and some research activities in order to achieve optimal complementarity and synergy with their objectives (e.g. risk assessment, databases, etc.).</p>
Specific needs	Harmonisation of surveillance programs relevant to AMR, FBZ and ET to the extent possible, and use of standardized testing [4, 5, 9].	<p>Given the participation of 19 European countries, and given the strong cross-sectoral prospective of One Health EJP, overarching work on harmonization and alignment of procedures has high potential.</p> <p>Projects of One Health EJP deal with analysis, integration and standardization of methods, surveillance data (including WGS) and metadata across the medical and veterinary sector (e.g. ORION, COHESIVE, IMPART and NOVA).</p> <p>In addition, all novel field surveillance methodologies, guidelines and protocols developed by One Health EJP members (see section below) are harmonized already at an early stage.</p>

<p>Reporting at the national, regional and global level, and between all the stakeholders, focusing on the flexibility of reporting tools and comparability of results through shared databases [1-3, 7-9, 11].</p>	<p>One Health EJP and its consortium members are contributing to the FAO/OIE/WHO Tripartite Zoonoses Guide (TZG) [11] by sharing information on tools and resources to establish a coordinated One Health surveillance system for zoonotic diseases in the frame of the Tripartite Surveillance and Information Sharing Operational Toolkit.</p> <p>In addition, specific projects aim at smoothening cross-boundary and cross-sector surveillance by comparing descriptors and data of national surveillance systems and databases (e.g. ORION), as well as exploring ways in which information is shared at different levels (e.g. COHESIVE) and the barriers that frustrate communication (e.g. NOVA). In line with global trends, high importance is given to AMR (e.g. ARDIG).</p>
<p>Benchmarking/evaluating monitoring and risk assessment activities along the food supply chain, with particular focus on AMR (pathogens and genes) [1, 3, 4].</p>	<p>Members of One Health EJP have developed computational methods and pipelines not just to monitor the food chain, but also to benchmark appropriate monitoring and risk assessment methods (e.g. COHESIVE and RaDAR), including assessing the cost saving impact of surveillance strategies (e.g. NOVA).</p>
<p>Novel sustainable and affordable ways of detection of AMR [1, 4].</p>	<p>One Health EJP is in the frontline of developing fast, cost-sensitive, novel technologies for sampling (e.g. AIR SAMPLE) and AMR detection (e.g. IMPART, METASTAVA). These range from metagenomic arrays (e.g. MAD-Vir) to pen-side methodologies (e.g. TOX detect), and focus on a range of bacteria like, but not restricted to, <i>Salmonella</i>, <i>Campylobacter</i>, <i>E. coli</i> (e.g. MoMIR-PPC), <i>Klebsiella</i> (e.g. MedVetKlebs) and <i>C. difficile</i> (IMPART).</p> <p>As mentioned above, all this methodologies are harmonized at an early stage between sectors and across borders.</p>

Integration of whole genome sequencing (WGS) data and metadata in quantitative risk assessment [15, 16].	<p>One Health EJP aims at optimizing the value of sequencing data and metadata, in order to use them for risk assessment (e.g. MedVetKlebs), source attribution (e.g. RaDAR), and diagnostic purposes (e.g. METASTAVA) in the veterinary and public health sector.</p> <p>Databases for molecular typing data and metadata are being explored (e.g. COHESIVE) and models for such integration are being developed for a number of pathogens (e.g. LISTADAPT).</p>
Cost analysis of risk management activities [1, 3]	<p>Models and analysis frameworks to assess cost effectiveness of procedures are developed by One Health EJP projects (e.g. ORION, COHESIVE). Innovative mathematical models align risk management activities with cost effectiveness considerations (e.g. MoMIR-PPC) aiming to amend the effectiveness of biosecurity measures.</p> <p>In addition our proposed intervention strategies and novel detection techniques feature cost benefit analysis (e.g. AIR SAMPLE).</p>
Development of national One Health policy guidelines and plans [7, 10, 11]	<p>The integrated One Health EJP activity COHESIVE is drafting and will implement a European One Health policy guide, in line with the FAO/OIE/WHO Tripartite Zoonoses Guide (TZG) [11], strengthening the collaboration between human-veterinary-food -environmental sector.</p>

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